

**UNIVERSITY
OF GHANA**

INAUGURAL LECTURE

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TOPIC

The Pursuit of Health Amidst Scarcity:
Economics, Health, and the Romance In-Between

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Inaugural Lecture

by

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TITLE

The Pursuit of Health Amidst Scarcity Economics, Health, and the Romance In- Between

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INAUGURAL ADDRESS

SETTING THE STAGE

Madam Vice Chancellor, Pro Vice Chancellor(s), Provosts, Registrar, Deans and Directors, Heads of Academic Units, Members of Convocation, Ministers and Deputy Ministers of State, Members of Parliament, the Clergy, the Media, Partners and Collaborators in the room and online, Distinguished invited Guests, Students, Ladies and Gentlemen.

Thank you for the warm welcome. Before I begin, I wish to acknowledge how appreciative I am to all of you here in person and those joining virtually. I am truly humbled.

Lecture outline

My lecture will follow the following outline: I will start with some preliminaries, then provide some context to this journey of romance. I will then revisit theoretical and conceptual foundations that make a case for health economics. Thereafter, I will share some applications of economics to health, highlighting some of my life's work in this area, including in health technology assessments for policy. I will then share some thoughts on the role of health in economic development. Finally, I will highlight some areas that I plan to focus the rest of my career on.

Setting the Stage – Section Head – Prelude

In the spirit of humility, I think it prudent to share that crafting the frame for this lecture required careful and at times, challenging reflection, spanning several months and numerous revisions.

A Lecture of Continuation not Conclusion.

The foremost challenge was to decide:

Should this be a personal narrative charting my professional journey **or** a platform to address questions that some have posed about our discipline (health economics), offering insights into my life's work? After careful considerations, I will pursue both.

The announcement of this lecture also inspired some curiosity among my peers - some wondering if this event today would mark my academic

swansong.

I can assure you, with a wealth of years until retirement, my journey is far from complete.

So, to those who feared this might be my farewell lecture, fear not, I plan to be around for quite some time!

A Lecture of Tribute to Communal Craftsmanship

Madam Chair, from early childhood, I was well aware that my life was the product of '**communal craftsmanship.**' My 'small' family of parent and 21+ siblings was only the nucleus of this community - it extended to my parent's friends and clients, my teachers from elementary through tertiary education, and mentors from various social and religious groups.

This notwithstanding, I have been overwhelmed and deeply humbled by the show of love and support over the past weeks since this inaugural was announced. I thank you all. Today's occasion is not about celebrating me alone; rather, it is a tribute to the countless individuals who have worked behind the scenes to mold me into the person I am today.

I will revisit these acknowledgments in due course.

A Lecture of Romance in Health Economics?

Before moving on, allow me to shed light on a key term that headlines our discussion today and has sparked attention, and that is - 'romance!'

I assure you, I am no authority or master of relationships, yet my journey has been one that has yielded several insights about romance.

These have proven applicable to the intertwined relationship between health and economics, but also have echoed throughout my personal and professional life.

What does Romance have to do with it?

These are the touchstones that I will return to throughout this lecture.

on Attraction & Passion

Every romantic relationship springs from an initial attraction and is nourished by affection that deepens with time and effort. A shared passion serves as the glue for the relationship.

on the Element of Surprises:

Surprises infuse vibrant energy into relationships but also present opportunities for strengthening relationships.

on Challenges:

Every romance navigates through inevitable challenges, which require compromise and resilience.

on Trust:

Trust is the bedrock of any successful relationship. For a lasting, constructive relationship, trust should never be compromised.

on Optimism:

The vision of a brighter future, even amidst adversity, is crucial for enduring relationships.

Each of these facets weave together to define romance as we know it, and also, as I will share today - in the context of health economics and beyond.

1. THE JOURNEY OF ROMANCE: BEGINNINGS

The Unexpected Path to Economics

As a child, my aspirations, like those of many others, were far from the field of economics. In primary school, I dreamt of soaring through the skies as a pilot.

By the time I finished secondary school, I had set my sights on becoming a meteorologist.

This vision, once again, transformed when I began my undergraduate studies in Geography and Economics.

By my third year, I was deeply intrigued by Geomorphology - the study of the Earth's physical features and the processes that shape them.

However, at the dawn of my final undergraduate year, a twist of fate led me down a different path.

Recognizing my consistent performance in Economics, and on the advice of a friend, I decided to specialize in Economics, setting aside my initial interest in Geography but not without pain.

My journey, much like a romantic relationship, began with attraction to diverse fields, but eventually, I found myself irresistibly drawn to Economics.

Romancing Health Economics

My initiation into the realm of health economics happened during my undergraduate project in my final year.

Prof. Samuel K. Anim, my statistical economics lecturer at the time (now the Government Statistician), sought to convince a group of friends and I towards researching HIV/AIDS. However, Dr. Peter Aglobitse, our assigned supervisor, steered us towards an emerging topic of the day - the National Health Insurance Bill of 2003. Our exploration into people's willingness to participate in the scheme became my gateway into the world of health economics.

As part of the research, I had the opportunity to conduct fieldwork, run a series of logit regressions, and prepare a report. This laid the foundation for my master's thesis, where I delved deeper into the realm of health economics, finance and investment.

My affection for health economics had blossomed, and there was no turning back.

A golden opportunity offered by Professors Moses Aikins and Johnny Gyapong led me to pursue a PhD in public health, specializing in health economics.

2. THEORETICAL AND CONCEPTUAL CASE FOR HEALTH ECONOMICS

Economics as a Social Science

Economics is a social science that studies human behavior as it relates unlimited wants to scarce means, which evokes the concept of efficiency. That is, scarce resources must be used in a way that that we achieve the most of them.

It echoes the constraints and sacrifices we often encounter in romantic relationships - making difficult decisions to allocate our limited resources most efficiently and equitably. Each decision we make comes at a cost - utilizing a resource for one purpose means denying the benefits from its potential use for another. Economists call this 'opportunity cost.'

Thus, in the face of scarce resources, the essence of efficiency is choosing options that maximize outcomes and minimize opportunity cost.

Why Health Economics?

Why is Health Economics Important, you may ask?

In an ideal world, we would have unlimited resources to combat every health threat, be it diseases of all kinds or potential epidemics or pandemics.

The reality, however, is starkly different, as we have more wants than the available resources to attain them.

The field of health economics helps decision-makers at various levels make the best use of our limited resources, thereby maximizing health outcomes and minimizing opportunity costs.

Health is Wealth

The age-old saying, "Health is Wealth," encapsulates the intricate relationship between health and economic development.

Importance of Relationship Valued throughout the History of Economic Thought

Several theories emphasize this relationship between economics and health, though sometimes implicitly. They all argue that a healthy labor force significantly influences economic growth.

The contributions of renowned economists like Francois Quesnay (1694-1774), Adam Smith (1723-1790), and Thomas Malthus (1766-1790), among others, highlight the role of health as an essential ingredient in economic growth through:

- Welfare of farmers and their families (Quesnay)
- Working population in productive labor (Smith)
- Unchecked population which leads to poverty, reducing growth (Malthus).

These and several other studies (Grossman, 1975; Becker, 1975; Lucas, 1988; Becker et al., 1990) indicate a strong bidirectional relationship between health and economic development.

The Dilemma

However, if health is such a crucial productive input to economic growth, why is it not prioritized in economic and development plans?

Why do we witness significant underinvestment in health?

We will revisit these thought-provoking questions later in this lecture.

3. ENACTING CHANGE: APPLICATIONS OF HEALTH ECONOMICS

My work within health economics has primarily revolved around policy-oriented research, where I generate evidence to aid decision-making.

This typically involves engaging with decision-makers, grasping their evidence requirements, and refining my research inquiries to accommodate these needs. It involves many back-and-forth interactions with decision-makers.

Although the journey has not always been smooth – navigating complex bureaucratic procedures and adjusting my academic approach—it has been immensely rewarding.

Now, let us delve into two principal areas where economics intersects with health – economic evaluations/HTAs and health financing.

I will share some examples from my own work in these areas.

Evidence-Informed Priority Setting – More Health for the Money

As mentioned earlier, health economics arms us with the necessary tools to make efficient decisions, helping us optimize the use of limited societal resources.

Again, as indicated earlier, health economics provides tools to support decision-making that is efficient, optimizing the use of scarce societal resources.

I have led and contributed to studies which make use of health economics techniques to inform decision-making.

I will discuss a few of these highlights here:

Malaria Interventions - Home-based care for children and seasonal malaria chemoprevention

In 2004, the World Health Organization (WHO) promoted the expansion of home-based management of malaria (HMM)¹ based on data from some countries, acknowledging that prompt and effective management near the home could save many lives.

The HMM strategy involves training community volunteers to identify and manage non-severe malaria in children and refer severe malaria cases to nearest health facilities.

In 2005, Professor Johnny Gyapong received substantial funding to conduct a clinical trial testing the impact of HMM and potential impact of extending the approach to cover other febrile illnesses such as pneumonia, in Ghana. I was one of three doctoral researchers and I was assigned to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of the interventions.

Our study was one of the most formative studies showing that under certain conditions, HMM is cost-effective². It was also first to evaluate the approach's expansion to cover pneumonia, proving its impact³ and cost-effectiveness.

This study provided crucial evidence for scaling up the home-based care strategy nationwide by the malaria elimination programme and contributed to global evidence.

Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention (SMC)

Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention aims to prevent malaria by distributing monthly doses of preventive treatment ahead of the main malaria season, in areas of with seasonal transmission such as the Sahel region of Africa.

In 2015, I led a team from SPH to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of SMC in Ghana, which contributed evidence to scaling up SMC across the northern regions of the country⁴.

Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention (SMC)

¹ WHO 2004: [Scaling up home-based management of malaria : from research to implementation \(who.int\)](https://www.who.int/publications/m/item/scaling-up-home-based-management-of-malaria-from-research-to-implementation)

² Nonvignon et al. (2012): [Is home management of fevers a cost-effective way of reducing under-five mortality in Africa? The case of a rural Ghanaian District - Nonvignon - 2012 - Tropical Medicine & International Health - Wiley Online Library](https://doi.org/10.1186/14752875-5-1)

³ [Impact of Community Management of Fever \(Using Antimalarials With or Without Antibiotics\) on Childhood Mortality: A Cluster-Randomized Controlled Trial in Ghana in: The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene Volume 87 Issue 5 Suppl \(2012\) \(ajtmh.org\)](https://doi.org/10.1186/14752875-5-1)

⁴ Nonvignon et al. (2016): [Cost-effectiveness of seasonal malaria chemoprevention in upper west region of Ghana | Malaria Journal | Full Text \(biomedcentral.com\)](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12918-016-0288-8)

This study also laid the foundation for later research, including evaluating large-scale SMC implementation in seven West African countries⁵.

Currently, research is underway to explore other potential products, such as monoclonal antibodies, for SMC administration. I am leading a team to address gaps in understanding comprehensive costs of SMC and potential cost-effectiveness of new alternatives.

Introducing New Vaccines and Switching Vaccine Products

Vaccines are pivotal in public health, substantially reducing disease-related morbidity and mortality.

Health economics has significantly contributed to decisions to introduce new or switch existing vaccines, and my efforts and evidence generation in this area has involved cost and cost-effectiveness analyses of several vaccines, such as those targeting **rotavirus diarrhea**^{6,7,8}, **cervical cancer**⁹ **malaria**¹⁰ **as well as COVID-19 vaccines, and treatments**^{11,12,13,14}.

Childhood vaccines

On: **Childhood vaccines: cost-effective public health interventions**

Rotavirus (for diarrhea), HPV (for cervical cancer), and RTS,S (for malaria) vaccination programs demonstrate success in reducing illness and mortality, representing value-for-money in the use of scarce resources.

COVID-19 vaccines and treatments

⁵ Gilmartin et al. (2021): [Seasonal malaria chemoprevention in the Sahel subregion of Africa: a cost-effectiveness and cost-savings analysis - The Lancet Global Health](#)

⁶ Nonvignon et al. (2018): [Cost-effectiveness of rotavirus vaccination in Ghana: Examining impacts from 2012 to 2031 - ScienceDirect](#)

⁷ Owusu et al. (2023): [Rotavirus vaccine product switch in Ghana: An assessment of service delivery costs, switching costs, and cost-effectiveness | PLOS Global Public Health](#)

⁸ Pecenka et al. (2020): [Cost-effectiveness analysis for rotavirus vaccine decision-making: How can we best inform evolving and complex choices in vaccine product selection? - ScienceDirect](#)

⁹ Vodicka et al. (2022): [The projected cost-effectiveness and budget impact of HPV vaccine introduction in Ghana - ScienceDirect](#)

¹⁰ Sicuri et al. (2019): [The Costs of Implementing Vaccination With the RTS,S Malaria Vaccine in Five Sub-Saharan African Countries - Elisa Sicuri, Fadima Yaya Bocoum, Justice Nonvignon, Sergi Alonso, Bakar Fakh, George Bonsu, Simon Kariuki, Oscar Leeuwenkamp, Khatia Munguambe, Mwifadhi Mrisho, Vincent Were, Christophe Sauboin, 2019 \(sagepub.com\)](#)

¹¹ Nonvignon et al. (2022): [Estimating the cost of COVID-19 vaccine deployment and introduction in Ghana using the CVIC tool - ScienceDirect](#)

¹² Africa CDC Policy Brief (2023): [Optimizing Strategies for COVID-19 Vaccine Roll-out in Benin and Ghana – Africa CDC](#)

¹³ Liu et al. (2023): [Assessing the impacts of COVID-19 vaccination programme's timing and speed on health benefits, cost-effectiveness, and relative affordability in 27 African countries | BMC Medicine | Full Text \(biomedcentral.com\)](#)

¹⁴ Edeka et al. [A cost-effectiveness analysis of Molnupiravir and Paxlovid in three African countries | medRxiv](#)

On: COVID-19 Vaccines and Therapeutics

Investments in pandemic prevention, preparedness and response, including vaccinations and treatments are cost-effective, and present good economic returns.

Madam Chair, these studies validate that vaccines and vaccinations are efficient public health measures under various conditions. Vaccines save lives.

They guide decision-makers to identify critical parameters that enable or impede the efficiency of vital public health interventions.

Thus, these studies highlight the "best buys" and the "most effective ways" to minimize resource waste, particularly in resource-limited settings like Africa.

4. HEALTH TECHNOLOGY ASSESSMENT FOR POLICY-MAKING

Health Technology Assessments (HTA) serve as critical tools for embedding efficiency into decision-making

To assist national policymakers in integrating efficiency into their decisions and facilitate optimal utilization of limited societal resources, health economists frequently resort to evidence-informed priority-setting (EIPS) mechanisms, such as health technology assessments. HTA allows for a comprehensive assessment of the costs, cost-effectiveness, budget impact and other facets of health technologies and interventions (integrating ethical and equity considerations, among others) to inform decision-making and enhance overall health service delivery and outcomes.

There have been debates about the relevance of such evidence-informed decision-making in the current context, especially in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where a significant portion of health spending comes from donors. I firmly assert that this approach is more pertinent now than ever.

However, previous attempts to persuade policymakers in LMICs to adopt this method have not led to the expected behavioral changes, particularly in Africa. I will touch on this topic in more detail shortly.

Focusing on the Outcome, not Just the Process: A Case Study from Ghana

Often, an excessive focus is placed on the procedures of evidence-informed decision-making, sidelining the importance of the eventual outcome.

This is evident from the few studies which have examined the impact of mechanisms like HTA on health outcomes.

As researchers and practitioners, we must never lose sight of our ultimate goal: improving population health.

Health Technology Assessments serve as critical tools for embedding efficiency into decision-making

On: Resource Optimization - HTA of Childhood Cancers

Let me share some work that I have been involved in within this realm. I co-chair the HTA Technical Working Group of Ghana's Ministry of Health, which has evaluated the impact of health technologies, medicines and influenced policy decisions.

For instance, before 2021, treatment for childhood cancers in Ghana was not covered by the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS), placing a considerable financial burden on affected families.

In 2020, the TWG set out to assess the potential impacts of covering Burkitt Lymphoma treatments under the NHIS, using disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) as an outcome measure.

Our assessment¹⁵ concluded that this inclusion represents a value-for-money in use of societal resources, contributing to the NHIS coverage of childhood cancers from November 2021 onwards¹⁶.

I ask the critics of evidence-informed priority setting:

WAS IT NOT BENEFICIAL TO UNDERTAKE STUDIES THAT LED TO ALLEVIATING FAMILIES' BURDENS AND SAVING THE LIVES OF MANY CHILDREN IN GHANA?

Countries like Thailand and, some African countries like Ghana, Tunisia,

¹⁵ [Final-Report-HTA-Burkitts-Lymphoma.pdf \(moh.gov.gh\)](#)

¹⁶ [News \(nhis.gov.gh\)](#)

Egypt, Kenya, and South Africa have taken steps to incorporate evidence-informed priority setting into national health decisions.

Our health sectors operate under severe resource constraints, and we must make better use of economic evidence in our decisions.

Opportunities for Institutionalizing EIPS in Africa

The most significant obstacle to institutionalizing EIPS is capacity. Policymakers often lack the ability to understand and demand, and researchers to supply, evidence based on policy needs.

This deficiency has led to well-intentioned yet ill-fitting programs designed, including by external partners.

Another challenge is the low visibility for evidence-informed priority setting within the policy sphere. There is room to improve on policy visibility (including use of policy champions, a strong finance-health interface, civil society engagements and potential legislation to entrench use of EIPS). Furthermore, there are opportunities for capacity initiatives tailored to policymaker needs, and other training programmes on EIPS in our academic institutions.

Africa Health Technology Assessment Programme (AfHTAP)

To mitigate these challenges, the Africa CDC HEP has launched the Africa HTA Programme (AfHTAP), aiming to develop a continental framework for evidence-informed priority setting and build local capacities to drive its institutionalization.

Objective:

Empower Member States to take charge of their own evidence-informed priority-setting processes - to foster efficient and effective utilization of domestic resources, thereby maximizing health outcomes.

Goals:

- Create an enabling environment for sustainable, evidence-based priority setting in Health.
- Provide an adaptable and flexible guide tailored to the unique needs and circumstances of each country to foster context-specific public health initiatives and sustainable partnerships, affirming Africa CDC's vital position in this process.
- Comprehensive tool to address critical health management

aspects, including health technology assessment, governance, financing, and capacity building.

- Intended for a wide range of stakeholders: Member States, regional partners, and global partners.

The Future of Evidence-Informed Policy-Making in Africa

Madam Vice Chancellor, Invited Guests, Ladies and Gentlemen, I advocate for a collaborative approach between academic partners and Ministries of Health; country-based universities and researchers should be feeding Ministries with evidence and capacity, while partnering with external universities where needed. Funders need to support more of such initiatives that tap into and strengthen country capacity.

Harmonizing these efforts across the continent will allow Africa to steer its future, in line with the African Union Agenda 2063: The Africa We Want

5. THE FORGOTTEN PARTNER: HEALTH IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Is Health Forgotten in Economic Development?

Madam Vice Chancellor, the relationship between health and economic development is not dissimilar to a romance, characterized by strong attraction, mutual dependency, and the necessity for continuous investment and commitment.

However, it seems that in the arena of development, health is often the unseen partner, notably underinvested in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs).

WE ARE LEFT QUESTIONING WHERE THIS CRUCIAL RELATIONSHIP IS LEADING US?

The Paradox of Health Prioritization and Underinvestment in Africa

Although a strong link exists between health and economic development and many commitments have been made to boost health funding, many African countries appear to not prioritize health investments.

To illustrate this, in the 2001 Abuja Declaration, African nations pledged to assign at least 15% of their annual budgets to health.

More than a decade since, many countries fall short of their promises, dedicating less than 10% of their annual budgets to health.

In fact, since 2001, only 1 - 3 countries have achieved the Abuja target annually. As an example, Ghana has yet to reach this objective.

Is Health Forgotten in Economic Development?

The average domestic government health expenditure in Sub-Saharan Africa is \$73.79 per capita, with some countries spending as low as \$16.42. These averages expose stark disparities among different income groups in the region and compares with \$594 for Latin America and the Caribbean. Again, the average current health expenditure as a percentage of gross domestic product (GDP) is 4.92 in sub-Saharan Africa, 6.94 in East Asia and the Pacific. Clearly, sub-Saharan Africa lags behind its peers in health spending.

IS THERE HELP FROM GLOBAL FINANCING ARCHITECTURE FOR AFRICA?

Dependence on Development Assistance for Health

In Africa, a significant percentage of total health expenditure originates from donors – 22% average for Africa compared to 7% for South East Asia and 2% for the Americas. Donor dependence remains a major part of low-income country (LIC) health budget. In South Sudan and Zimbabwe, 64% and 56% of current health expenditure originates from donors¹⁷.

The gaps in financing leaves people with no choice than spend out of pocket, which is high and worsens the plight of the poor and vulnerable.

This heavy reliance on Development Assistance for Health (DAH) often results in health priorities being shaped by donors rather than national governments.

While DAH plays a pivotal role in supporting health delivery and improving health outcomes, it is not without flaws. Its current model raises critical questions about its sustainability and future.

Donor governments, unsurprisingly, tend to prioritize their own needs and interests above those of recipient countries.

This was explicitly demonstrated during the COVID-19 pandemic when

¹⁷ [External health expenditure \(EXT\) as percentage of current health expenditure \(CHE\) \(%\) \(who.int\)](#)

many donor nations pre-ordered the majority of available vaccines only to store them and "donate" to developing countries close to expiry of vaccines (often with a public show)^{18,19,20,21}.

The current architecture of DAH has been criticized (and I am one such strong critics), as it often perpetuates inequities and deviates from its supposed role as a global health "savior".

Health at Stake: Confronting the Debt Crisis

One major obstacle to increasing domestic financing for health remains high interest payments on debt.

Payments or People?

The burden of interest payments is outpacing other critical areas of public spending, **as demonstrated by a recent UN publication**²².

Countries are grappling with an unenviable dilemma – choosing between honoring their debt obligations or prioritizing the well-being of their people. Interest payments have taken precedence over serving the people.

Shockingly, 3.3 billion individuals reside in nations where interest payments surpass investments in education and health. This mounting debt burden jeopardizes prosperity for both humanity and the planet.

In Africa, the amount spent on interest payments is higher than spending on either education or health, with health suffering the most.

Clearly, the multilateral financing system, too, needs an overhaul, as it motivates countries to prioritize interest payments over critical social services like health.

Should Africa be dependent on global health financing institutions?

Global health financing mechanisms such as Global Fund, Gavi the vaccine alliance, Pandemic Fund all play a critical role in supporting delivery of health services in Africa.

However, they cannot alleviate all our health problems. Africa needs to

¹⁸ [The huge waste of expired Covid-19 vaccines \(lemonde.fr\)](https://www.lemonde.fr)

¹⁹ [Covid vaccine doses go to waste in Switzerland amid huge stockpile - SWI swissinfo.ch](https://www.swissinfo.ch)

²⁰ [Poorer nations reject over 100 mln COVID-19 vaccine doses as many near expiry | Reuters](https://www.reuters.com)

²¹ [Europe donated near-expired doses of vaccine to African countries \(qz.com\)](https://www.qz.com)

²² UN Global Crisis Response Group (GCRG) on Food, Energy and Finance. 2023. [A world of debt | UNCTAD](https://unctad.org)

take more responsibility in driving and financing solutions to its problems. We must help ourselves, and not fully depend on others.

Spotlight on Ghana's Health Budget

The debt situation notwithstanding, there are opportunities for governments of SSA countries to improve their health spending.

While the Government of Ghana has over the years commendably increased budgetary allocation to health, not all of the money gets released. Even what gets released is not fully utilized; does this mean we already have enough to spend? We need to improve our public financial management systems and incorporate priority setting to inject efficiency.

That notwithstanding, the around \$1 billion allocation to health, including the NHIS is not adequate. In half year 2022, health was the second largest contributor to GDP, only behind the services sector.

Therefore, we need to identify innovative ways to significantly increase the health budget, for example, through:

- Maintaining the COVID-19 levy, which could raise between \$100 – 600 million annually for health (public health emergency). I advocate for keeping, not scrapping this levy as it could raise about 60% additional resources for health on top of current health budget.
- Taking advantage of special programmes to support health. Of 16 special programmes in the 2023 national budget with total budget of GHS 9 billion, only one is health specific – nursing training allowance (2.8% of total).
 - Opportunities exist to introduce programmes targeting, for example, malaria elimination, growing burden of mental health and non-communicable diseases, etc.

The COVID-19 Pandemic: Wake-Up call or Awakening of Romance?

The COVID-19 pandemic serves as a grim reminder of the intricate relationship between health and economic development.

Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic:

Globally, the pandemic resulted in more than 760 million cases and approximately 7 million deaths, with estimates showing that the pandemic contributed to about 19 million excess deaths, that is 2.7 times more than the recorded deaths; 12 million cases and over 250,000+ deaths in Africa;

over 170,000 cases and over 1,400 deaths in Ghana.

These statistics represent painful losses of lives, but also significant **losses in economic outputs** through reduced productive activity, leading to increased spending that has now put many countries at risk of debt distress (or at least contributed largely to their current state).

In Africa alone, 22 countries are in or at high risk of debt distress, with our beloved Ghana being one of those. The pandemic is estimated to have led to reduction in global economic growth by 3% a few months after it hit²³.

But the pandemic also had many channels of **contributing to reduced economic growth**. For example, for air travel alone, the pandemic led to about 60%, 49% and 29% reductions in passenger numbers in 2020, 2021 and 2022, respectively (compared to 2019 levels). The total loss in gross passenger operating revenues for airlines are estimated to be \$372 billion, \$324 billion, and \$175 billion in 2020, 2021 and 2022, respectively (compared to 2019 levels)²⁴. Again, the pandemic led to significant rise in unemployment that has also pushed households further down the poverty drain. One is yet to consider the future impact of school closures and other measures – in some countries like Uganda, where schools were closed for almost two years (22 months).

Dance of Danger

Madam Vice Chancellor, Ladies and Gentlemen, the COVID-19 pandemic was a stark reminder of the significant economic losses a health crisis can engender.

With the considerable toll it took on all sectors, the pandemic underscored the scale of economic impact that a health crisis could have, **prompting us to ponder - what if we were faced with multiple pandemics of the same severity, simultaneously?**

Yet, Africa faces more than 100 health threats annually, albeit at different levels of severity, further highlighting the importance of investing in health for sustained economic development.

A NEED OF THE HOUR: A CALL TO ACTION FOR EMPOWERING AFRICA'S FUTURE

²³ [World Economic Outlook \(imf.org\)](https://www.imf.org)

²⁴ https://www.icao.int/sustainability/Documents/Covid-19/ICAO_coronavirus_Econ_Impact.pdf

Urgent Action on Health Prioritization

We are now standing at the brink of an era that demands urgent action from African nations. Just as innovation keeps the spark alive in a romance, now is the time for Africa to espouse commitment and ownership of her health agenda, boldly pursuing innovative health financing mechanisms to raise domestic resources and decrease donor dependence.

Placing Health at the Heart of Development

Africa needs to rethink and boldly act. Health is our lifeline; universal health coverage requires bold financing decisions: we need to act by

1. Prioritizing health in national development agendas
2. Treating Health as an Investment: Health is not merely a social good; it is an investment with quantifiable returns, not merely cost.
3. Take Ownership of Health: It is crucial that Africa takes charge of her health and prioritizes investments from domestic sources.

Overhaul the current architecture of Donor Assistance

While advising the mouse to stay out of the way of the cat, it is also prudent to send a message to the cat.

There is an urgent need to overhaul the current architecture of DAH:

1. To ensure that DAH serves its purpose in the future of global health.
2. Donor financing should be a catalyst for government spending, not crowd out same.
 - Donor funds could target critical public health functions e.g., surveillance, research, development and innovation.
 - Governments need to take responsibility, financing to target goods, services, human resource.
3. A significant portion of DAH finances so-called technical assistance (TA), mainly externally driven. True and sustainable TA is one that strengthens country expertise for sustainability.

Bold, innovative and collective action to raise domestic resources for health

There is an urgent need for innovative ways of financing Africa's Health from domestic resources:

1. Urgent (individual country and collective) actions are required by governments to boldly raise domestic resources for country and cross-country public health functions.
2. Identify and mobilize resources from private sector by providing conducive environment and presenting economic case for private sector financing
3. Raise and deploy critical mass of globally competitive African minds to represent Africa's voice in the global health and international financing architecture and promote equity – this is what Africa needs – the Africa We Want!

The Director General of Africa CDC advocates for innovative financing mechanisms like airline levies and funding from multilateral development banks (MDBs) to finance the New Public Health Order and safeguard our health security.

- *18 countries already utilize airline levies to support UNITAID globally*
- *A modest \$1-20 per ticket (varying with class and route) could raise up to \$2 billion over 5 years for critical public health functions.*

Madam Vice Chancellor, Ladies and Gentlemen, it is important to revisit the tory of romance between health and economics. Health and economics (or economic development) have a strong attraction, but the relationship has not received the attention and commitment it deserves. Severe under-investments in health have led to consequences for the economy as a result of health shocks. These surprises are opportunities to build trust and rekindle the romantic relationship. There is optimism but it requires a redirection of the attention and commitment to invest in health.

6. LOOKING AHEAD: A PERSONAL AGENDA AND INVITATION

My personal journey in health economics, much like a romantic relationship, has been full of ups and downs, moments of profound joy and deep challenge, and surprises along the way. Navigating disagreements, making tough decisions, and nurturing trust have been integral parts of my journey.

But overall, each experience has enriched my career and added to a rewarding journey.

Not Farewell but Forward

Madam Vice Chancellor, today does not mark my academic swansong; instead, it propels me forward to explore new horizons of impact and growth.

So, how do I intend to devote my efforts for the journey ahead?

Permit me to share a glimpse of the path I plan to pursue in the coming years.

A Journey Unfinished

Building Capacity:

Firstly, I firmly believe in building capacity through enhancing training opportunities. To expand the capacity to teach and practice health economics, there is need to consciously support Health Economics programs, nurturing policy-oriented graduates who will spearhead health reforms.

Just as a strong foundation is crucial in any successful relationship, universities must play a pivotal role in supporting incubation of Health Economics programs.

The fertile grounds for practicing health economics in Africa call for expansion, with more programs and courses dedicated to this field.

To spearhead health reforms and amplify Africa's voice in global initiatives, we need to nurture policy-oriented graduates who will champion Africa's interests.

Mentoring for Growth:

Secondly, mentoring for growth is essential, much like nurturing a thriving romance. I am committed to investing in mentoring young talents aspiring to make a meaningful impact in public health.

By empowering and guiding them, we can create a generation of health economists dedicated to advocating for Africa's health priorities.

Engaging policymakers:

Thirdly, engaging policymakers is crucial. In any relationship, asserting our needs and expectations is vital, and the same applies to health economics. Policy visibility elevates the role of health economics in critical

reforms and embeds the importance of domestic capacity to drive them. We must ensure our voice is heard in decision-making processes, institutionalizing the use of health economics and financing evidence. Initiatives such as the partnership between WHO Ghana, MOH Ghana, and UG SPH in training MOH staff on health economics are commendable and should be replicated continent-wide.

Collaborative efforts between academic partners and Ministries of Health and Finance will be pivotal, with country-based universities and researchers taking the lead in providing evidence and capacity to drive policy changes.

Empowering Africa's Position on the Global Health Landscape:

Lastly, Africa's position on the global health landscape demands a shift in perspectives and priorities. Just as balance and alignment are crucial in a thriving relationship, we must realign funders' perspectives to support sustainable approaches.

Unsustainable practices must give way to empowering country-led initiatives that leverage external resources. By adopting this approach, Africa can ascend to a more significant role in shaping the global health agenda.

Let us seize the opportunity to reclaim our narrative, prioritize our continent's health, and advocate for meaningful improvements.

I commit to these four areas – building capacity, mentoring the next generation of African Health Economists who will lead health reforms, continuously engaging policymakers, and empowering Africa's voice in the global health space.

Will you walk with me on this journey?

I call on partners to support such Africa-led initiatives. Respectful partnerships are key to sustainability. Africa is calling for respectful partnerships. And we need to be at the tables where decisions are made about Africa. Anything short of this is not respectful partnership.

Join in the Journey: an Invitation

Looking ahead– through the parallels between health economics and the intricacies of romance, we appreciate the passion, commitment, investment, capacity building, policy visibility, and the bright future that defines our field. The future in Africa is promising.

In closing, I extend an 'Invitation' to join this journey - intertwining the threads of scarcity, health, and the unique romance that weaves them together.

Let us further our own health, prioritizing our health, and keeping Africa's voice loud in the global health space where decisions that affect us are made.

Thank You

I thank you for accompanying me on this unfolding journey, that holds optimism as we continue to advance the field of health economics together. It promises to be a remarkable ride, full of discovery, challenge, and accomplishment. I thank you for your attention.